

Experimental studies on the influence of blisters on the load-bearing capacity of sandwich panels

Annalena Kühn^{*,a}, Christoph Haugwitz^b, Mario Kupnik^b, Jörg Lange^a

^aTechnical University Darmstadt, Institute for Steel Construction and Materials Mechanics, Germany
kuehn@stahlbau.tu-darmstadt.de

^bTechnical University Darmstadt, Measurement and Sensor Technology Group, Germany

ABSTRACT

Lightweight sandwich panels are an economical solution for wall and roof claddings. The panels consist of two thin faces of steel and a core with thermal insulating properties. The shear-resistant bond between faces and core results in a high load-bearing capacity combined with a low dead weight of the panels. Recently, polyisocyanurates (PIR) have been increasingly used as a core material instead of polyurethane (PUR). During service life, the panels may be damaged by blisters, when the outside of the façade is exposed to high temperatures. Thereby, the outer face separates from the core over a large area and the integrity of the load-transmitting components may be negatively affected as a result. The consideration of blistering in literature and in the standard (EN 14509) is limited to the durability of the panels. However, the load-bearing capacity of the panels may also be impaired depending on the size and position of a blister. Still, in practice, no design rules or recommendations are available for assessing the load-bearing capacity of blister-damaged panels. This article presents the results of experimental studies on the effect of large blisters on the load-bearing capacity and the concerning failure pattern of sandwich panels with a PIR-foam core. Carrying out six-point-bending-tests with artificially inserted blisters, the maximum failure loads and failure patterns are recorded for this purpose. The aim is to analyse the effects of blisters in dependence of their position and to gain an understanding of the resulting type of failure. First results reveal a possibly significant influence for blisters located centrally at midspan. It also became apparent that the direction and velocity of blister propagation determine whether a blister affects the component failure or not. Thus, the load capacity of the tested panels was in some cases significantly reduced compared to undamaged reference panels.

Keywords: Lightweight steel constructions, sandwich panels, PIR-foam core, blistering.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight steel constructions made of sandwich panels have emerged in the last decades as an important branch of the construction industry, particularly in industrial buildings. The panels, consisting of two thin faces of steel and a polyurethane (PU) or mineral wool core embedded between them, function as wall and roof claddings and fulfil all requirements for an economical building envelope. From the shear-resistant bond between the faces and the core, a high load-bearing capacity is achieved coupled with a low dead weight of the panels. Regarding the core material, there is a continuous development in terms of foam formulations. Over the past few years, the use of polyisocyanurates (PIR) instead of polyurethane (PUR) as core material has increased. Changes in the mechanical characteristics are associated with this, resulting in a continuous need for research.

Due to their use as façade elements, sandwich panels are exposed to very high temperature stresses caused by solar radiation. As a result, the components may be damaged by the formation of blisters. Thus, the outer face delaminates from the core and an outward warping becomes visible. While the appearance of the façade may be impaired, this can also lead to a reduction in the load-bearing capacity. Furthermore, the occurrence of blisters has been increasingly observed in practice since the use of PIR has expanded (1) An extensive analysis of expert reports in (2) revealed this problem being an issue that effects the entire industry. Although some aspects of blistering have already been considered in previous research (1; 2; 3), the cause for the occurrence of blisters have not yet been completely unravelled. In addition to the influence of a high face temperature, the presence of production-related defects is identified as one of the necessary conditions for the occurrence of blisters (3).

A current research project at TU Darmstadt investigates the influence of defects in sandwich panels with a PIR-foam core. While (2) presents the results of experimental tests on the influence of various parameters on the formation of blisters, the present contribution focusses on the load-bearing capacity of blister-damaged sandwich panels. It aims to analyse the effects of blisters depending on their position within the panel. For this purpose, full scale tests were carried out on wall panels with artificially introduced blisters, whereby the maximum failure load and the type of failure were documented. It is of particular interest to consider when the inserted blisters lead to global failure and how they influence the failure mode compared to undamaged reference panels. By varying different parameters such as core depths and face thicknesses as well as different face profiles, the results are intended to provide important insights into blistering in sandwich panels and allow trends to be identified with regard to various parameters. Finally, the results obtained are evaluated regarding the assessment of blisters in practice.

2 STATE OF THE ART AND RESEARCH

Blistering in sandwich panels is a product- and manufacturer-wide issue that affects the entire industry. It is directly related to temperature exposure on the outside of the façade; in practice, most blisters are detected during the first year after the panels have been installed (2). The size of blisters varies over time as the environmental conditions change (e.g. cooling). Hence, the blisters can enlarge, but also recede. Regarding the formation of blisters in sandwich panels with a PUR-core, several observations and conclusions can be found in the literature. A detailed summary of these aspects is given in Kühn et al. (2). When analysing practical cases, the complexity of the problem becomes apparent, even if design and execution errors can be excluded. Depending on their number and size, the formation of blisters can have a huge impact on the façade's external appearance. In addition, the delamination of the face from the core is accompanied by an impairment of durability. As the delamination around the blisters eliminate the composite load-bearing effect, the integrity of the panels is negatively affected as well. In practice, especially in cases with many and large blisters, expert reports are required to assess whether the panels still have sufficient load-bearing capacity despite the damage (4). However, no standardised design rules and recommendations are available for this purpose. Ewert et al. (5) investigated the influence of defects in the composite between face and core in experimental and numerical studies. Nevertheless, the results did not provide any usable results for the production and design of sandwich panels. First attempts to consider a faulty bond between face and core by calculation are described by Pozorski and Pozorska (6) and by Das et al. (7), whereby the latter analyses refer to honeycomb cores for aeroplanes. However, it is problematic, that these approaches are not based on any kind of verified values for the defective compound. Due to a lack of investigations concerning the impact of existing blisters on the load-bearing capacity and failure of the components, sandwich wall panels with blisters are tested in six-point-bending-tests in this study. A comparison of the maximum bearing loads with undamaged reference panels and observations about the behaviour of the damaged areas during loading should provide initial trends about the effects of blisters. Furthermore, initial findings are to

be drawn from this to assess the residual load-bearing capacity of blister-damaged sandwich panels. These should take into account different product parameters.

3 EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

3.1 Preparation of test specimens

Artificial blisters were inserted into different standard-manufactured sandwich panels. Various parameters such as the thickness and profiling of the faces and the core depth were varied. Furthermore, the panels used were from different manufacturers. In order to separate the bond between face and core, an overpressure was introduced into the panel through a valve attached to the face over a small hole (*Fig. 1a*). The formation of blisters was then checked visually and by approximate sensing. Additionally, the size and orientation of the resulting blister were documented. When preparing the specimens, the success of the process varied depending on the face thickness, profiling of the face and adhesive strength between face and core. These differences become evident when considering the pressure required to insert the defect or blister (*Fig. 1b*). It was found that the pressure required on the thinner inner face of a panel is significantly lower than on the thicker outer face. In this case, the profiling of the faces and the lack of primer and consequently poorer adhesion on the inner face can also have an influence. Additionally, a variation between the analysed positions was observed. It should also be noted that the spread of the blister or delamination after the pressure has been applied is individual and cannot be predicted.

Fig. 1. a) Sandwich panel with artificial blisters; b) Comparison of the pressure required to insert the blister depending on the position and face thickness.

3.2 Experimental Program

The formation of blisters is often accompanied by a large-scale delamination of the outer face from the core, so that a negative impairment of the load-bearing capacity of the affected panel may be expected dependent on the size and position of the blister. To investigate this impairment, full scale tests according to EN 14509, Annex A.5 (8) were carried out in this study on sandwich wall panels with different product properties with artificially introduced blisters (*Fig. 1a*). The size of the blisters was estimated to be approximately 300 mm x 200 mm. Albeit the orientation of the longer side varied in the longitudinal and transverse direction of the panels. However, figure 2 qualitatively shows the selected positions of the valves used to apply the overpressure to the panel.

Each specimen was tested with only one valve and blister. At the time of loading, the blisters were no longer visible, but the localised delamination between the face and the core remained. Undamaged panels from the same production batch were tested as a reference. Table 1 contains a detailed summary of the tested specimens. The blisters were all located in the compression zone during the test. In the name of the test specimens, the abbreviation “*mfp*” means that the outer face was in the compression zone, whereas “*mfn*” indicates that the inner face was located in the compression zone. The components were loaded to failure during the test. Thereby, the force and deflection at midspan were continuously recorded. The type of failure was also documented for each test specimen and the deviation from the undamaged reference panel was determined as part of the evaluation.

Fig. 2. Different positions of the valves for introducing artificial blisters into the sandwich panel.

Table 1. Overview of the panels tested.

no.	Product properties	Name of specimen	Position of valve
1	Outer face: Steel, $t_N = 0.425$ mm, flat Inner face: Steel, $t_N = 0,420$ mm, lined Depth: D = 40 mm , Length: $L = 4000$ mm PIR-core (density: 37 kg/m^3)	Reference (n = 1)	-
		A_mfp_2_1	Position 3
		A_mfp_3_1	Position 4
2	Outer face: Steel, $t_N = 0.63$ mm, microprofiled Inner face: Steel, $t_N = 0,50$ mm, lined Depth: D = 60 mm , Length: $L = 5000$ mm PIR-core (density: 38 kg/m^3)	Reference (n = 3)	-
		B_mfp_2_1	Position 2
		B_mfp_3_1	Position 4
3	Outer face: Steel, $t_N = 0.63$ mm, microprofiled Inner face: Steel, $t_N = 0,50$ mm, lined Depth: D = 140 mm , Length: $L = 6000$ mm PIR-core (density: 38 kg/m^3)	Reference, <i>mfn</i> (n = 2)	-
		Reference, <i>mfp</i> (n = 2)	-
		C_mfp_3_1	Position 3
		C_mfn_4_2	Position 3
		C_mfp_5_1	Position 4
		C_mfn_6_1	Position 4
		C_mfp_7_1	Position 2
C_mfn_9_1	Position 1		

3.3 Results

The load-deflection-diagrams of the tested panels are shown in figures 3 a-d. Besides the ultimate loads of the panels, the failure modes of the specimens are also specified there. Regarding the reference panels, it should be noted that for the 40 mm thick panels one, for the 60 mm thick panels three and for the 140 mm thick panels two each were tested in the positive (*mfp*) and negative (*mfn*) position. A distinction is made in the designation of the types of failure as to whether wrinkling occurred at the load application or in the blister area.

The artificially introduced blisters and delaminations reduced the ultimate loads of the panels especially with the smaller depths of 40 and 60 mm. The reduction compared to the undamaged reference panels here was between 7% and 62%, depending on the panel type and location of the defect. The maximum measured reduction in load-bearing capacity of 62% occurred in the 40 mm thick panel with a centric blister at midspan. The eccentric blister at midspan led to a significantly lower reduction in the ultimate load. For the 60 mm thick panels with an eccentric blister, the position at midspan was found to be critical. However, there were relatively large differences between test specimens B_mfp_3_1 and B_mfp_3_2. Moreover, the blister in position 2, outside the maximum bending moment, also led to a conspicuous and non-negligible reduction of 14% in the ultimate load. In the 140 mm thick panels, the blisters were applied to both the inner and outer faces. Effects on the load-bearing capacity were only found on one panel with a centric defect on the outer face at midspan. There was a reduction in the ultimate load of approx. 16% compared to the undamaged reference panel. The deviations of the remaining panels are negligible.

Fig. 3. Load-deflection-diagrams of the panels tested with indication of the corresponding failure modes.

When comparing the failure modes between the reference and the damaged panel, it was found that the failure mode can change depending on the position of the blister. In several cases (A_mfp_3_1, B_mfp_3_1, B_mfp_3_2 and C_mfp_3_1), this resulted in a shift of the wrinkling into the defective area (Fig. 4a). This only occurred with a blister at midspan. Moreover, one of the specimens (A_mfp_2_1) failed due to delamination, which spread from the blister across the entire width of the panel (Fig. 4b). This can be clearly observed in the load-deformation-diagram as well (Fig. 3a). The bearable load was significantly reduced compared to the reference.

Fig. 4. a) B_mfp_3_2: Wrinkling failure in the blister area; b) A_mfp_2_1: Spreading of the delamination over the entire panel width.

A spread of the delamination in the transverse direction starting from the blister was observed in one of the 140 mm thick panels (C_mfp_3_1) as well. However, the delamination only spread over about half of the width, causing the panel to ultimately fail to wrinkling in the blister area (Fig. 5a). For this case, it can be concluded that the blister had an influence on the failure pattern, but with minor influence on the ultimate load. Additionally, a localised buckling of the faces in the blister area with immediate subsequent wrinkling failure on the load application occurred for the panels C_mfn_4_2 and C_mfn_6_1 (Fig. 5b). Further, two of the 140 mm thick specimens (C_mfp_5_1 and C_mfp_7_1) failed in shear like their corresponding references, with the delamination appearing to propagate longitudinally from the blister during the test. For the panel with the blister in the support area (C_mfn_9_1), neither a reduction in the load-bearing capacity nor any conspicuous behaviour was detected.

Fig. 5. a) C_mfp_3_1: Wrinkling failure due to the blister spreading over half the width of the panel; b) Local buckling in the blister area.

4 DISCUSSION

The test results indicate that positioning the blister at midspan, where the maximum bending stress applies, may be particularly critical. This is evident for all panels tested, except for specimens C_mfp_5_1 to C_mfn_6_1. In the latter, the method used to insert the blister or production-related differences could be possible reasons for this. However, there is no clear tendency between centric and eccentric position. Even a blister outside the maximum bending stress can lead to a reduction in load-bearing capacity, as the evaluation of B_mfp_2_1 shows. Based on the test results, a blister in

the support area appears to be the least critical. Neither an influence on the ultimate load nor on the failure pattern was found. The assumption that a shear failure could occur in this position was therefore not confirmed. However, even here the method of blister introduction cannot be completely ruled out as a cause.

Nevertheless, it is not only the position of the blister that determines whether it leads to failure. Whether a blister influences the component failure also depends significantly on the spread of the concerning delamination. This becomes particularly clear when comparing the specimens A_mfp_2_1 and C_mfp_3_1. In the former, the load-bearing capacity of the component was reached soon as the delamination extended across the entire width of the panel. In this case, the blister consequently led to global failure of the component and further load bearing is not possible. But if the blister only spreads over part of the panel width as in C_mfp_3_1, the components fail on wrinkling in the blister area, as in this case the bedding through the foam is only partial. For A_mfp_2_1, the propagation was significantly faster and at much lower load level compared to the corresponding reference panel than for C_mfp_3_1. This may be due to the different profiling of the faces, as the microprofiled face of C_mfp_3_1 may have greater resistance to crack propagation than the flat face of A_mfp_2_1 due to the existing beads. Another reason could be the adhesive strength of the bond between face and core, which may have been higher in C_mfp_3_1. The huge differences between the tested panels might also result from the method used to insert the blister, as the exact size and position of the delamination is not known. However, spreading of the delamination starting from the blister does not necessarily occur. As observed with C_mfn_4_2 and C_mfn_6_1, it is also possible that only localised buckling of the face occurs under loading. The local buckling does not lead to a reduction in the load-bearing capacity, as the load has relocated to intact areas and can therefore be increased even further. Here too, the lack of crack propagation in the transverse direction could result from the greater resistance due to the lining of the faces. Another cause can be found in the orientation of the initial blister. In cases where the delamination spread in the transverse direction, the blisters were aligned from the outset so that the length in the transverse direction (approx. 300 mm) was greater than the length in the longitudinal direction (approx. 200 mm). This was the opposite in the case of local buckling.

Based on the results, a correlation between the effect of blisters on the load-bearing capacity and the face thickness cannot be determined. Only a comparison of the pressure required to insert the blister showed that this tends to be lower with thinner faces. The higher impact of lower thickness is primarily due to the blister behaviour described above.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, the influence of blisters on the load-bearing capacity and the failure pattern of sandwich panels was investigated. Thereby, full scale tests were carried out on sandwich wall panels with a PIR-foam core and artificially introduced blisters. The blisters were positioned differently in order to identify dependencies on the position within the component. In order to induce the blisters, an overpressure was introduced into the panel through a valve. Due to this procedure, neither the exact position of the blister nor its exact size and orientation could be predetermined. The introduction of the blister is therefore not reproducible, meaning that it is not possible to compare several panels of the same type and blister position quantitatively. Nevertheless, the results obtained provide trends about the effects and behaviour of blister-damaged sandwich panels.

The results of this study show that an existing blister with an approx. size of 300 mm x 200 mm may have a significant influence on the load bearing capacity of the affected component. The resulting effects depend in part on the position of the blister within the component. Positioning the blister at midspan proved to be particularly critical for the panels tested. A clear tendency between centric and eccentric position was not detected. In contrast, a blister in the support area was found to be uncritical for the panels tested. Whether and at which level the component failure is affected

by the blister, however, also depends significantly on the direction and velocity of propagation, which is possibly determined by a combination of the face profiling and the adhesive strength between face and core. If the blister spread in the transverse direction, the load-bearing capacity was reduced by 7% to 62%, depending on the panel type. This was accompanied with a shift of the failure pattern to the blister-damaged area. Decisive for whether the component ultimately fails due to wrinkling or whether delamination occurs across the entire panel width is the velocity of blister propagation as well as the initial orientation of the blister. In the latter state, the panel was no longer capable of bearing, so that in practice replacement or repair would have to be considered from a structural point of view. If the propagation of the blister is prevented, only a localised buckling of the faces in the blister area occurs, without any effect on the load-bearing capacity. In this case, the component can withstand a further load, and, in practice, no replacement or repair would be necessary from a structural point of view. However, the development of the blister formation must be continuously monitored, as the propagation of the blister can have a significant impact on the load-bearing capacity. Regarding the influence of the smaller panel depths (40 and 60 mm) showed greater effects than the 140 mm thick panels. For the panels tested, this was entirely due to the behaviour during loading. Further tests and parameter studies are required to investigate this correlation more thoroughly. In addition, the parameter range will be expanded in further studies. This will also include and vary the size of the blister. Ultimately, a design guideline for blister-damaged sandwich panels may be developed.

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